

2025 NASA SMD Open Source Science Data Repositories Workshop

Governance Terms - In person
August 25, 2025

- Facilitators: Emily Foshee and Sam Berg
- Note-Taker: Farnaz
- Chat monitor: Grace Stewart

ALL DAY MATERIALS CAN BE FOUND HERE

Agenda

- Visit each of five activity stations in small groups (online visit breakout rooms)
- A bell will ring to signal change to another station - mix up and join a new group
- Governance Terms/Definitions/Synonyms - *Emily Foshee / Farnaz Bayat /Sam Berg*

Pre-Activity

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Speaker/Lightning Talk Notes

- Something like the 'Scos' schema may be helpful
- Did we use large language models to compile definitions across divisions
- Misusing the term 'variable' in ESDIS, understanding the difference between a data product (data product variable) vs. a collection (collection variable)
- Do you have the concept of data n*
- Archiving timeline means differently for each division (50 years - 100 years)
- Archiving timeline can be defined as long term or permanent (but what does permanent mean)
- In Helio, there is no solid repository
- Helio - does not use granule, granule means the physical
- File is mostly commonly used than granules (but planetary and ES use granule)
- You are looking for a dictionary
- Having a dictionary versus a thesaurus. Build a dictionary and you will have a thesaurus
- Using the term stakeholder across divisions - what can we replace it with
- Data product, vs, Data set, vs data collection
- These definitions
- Imagery: using image versus imagery

- Data appraisal
- Data repository can be an archiving center but an archive it's not necessarily a repository
- Definitions from astrophysics are missing

Webex Chat Comments

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Q&A

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